

Kaniadakis Entropy, The Notion of Moments and MaxEnt at $e/T \ll 1$ and $e/T \gg 1$

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Probability distributions in statistical mechanics are often considered as maximizing entropy. This entropy, however, may often be written in the form of an average $-\sum_i p(e_i) F(p(e_i))$ if $p(e_i) > 0$. For Shannon's entropy $F(p) = \ln(p)$. Entropy is then maximized usually with respect to average moments of e_i/T , with the zeroth and first order being the most commonly used. In (1), we argue that the constraints provide a statistical approximation of the physical system in terms of average moments. We then argue that $p(e_i)F(p(e_i))$ should also represent the same moments for consistency and this leads to the idea that $F(p(e_i)) = a + be_i$. Interestingly, this moment approach applies to the Maxwell-Boltzmann, Tsallis and Kaniadakis cases.

In order to maximize entropy, one has two terms $F(p(e_i)) + p \, dF/dp$. We argue that the first term reproduces $a + be_i$ (i.e. the constraint form), so $p \, dF/dp$ must do the same. An immediate pair of solutions are $F(p) = \ln(p)$ and $F(p) = p^k$. We ask: What happens when $e_i \rightarrow 0$. If one has $F(p) = p^k$, then $p(e) = g(e_i/T)^{1/k}$ is a solution such that $F(p) = g(e_i/T)$ as long as $g(e_i/T)$ behaves as $a + be_i$. This is of the form of $a(\ln(b e_i / (aT)))$, so in the $e_i/T \ll 1$ limit, one retrieves the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) form which is guaranteed to maximize entropy. In the $e_i/T \gg 1$ limit, $g(e_i/T)$ should behave as e_i/T . This form again maximizes entropy because of its power law nature. In the Tsallis case, $g(e_i) = 1 + ke_i/T$ which means that there is a straightforward transition from $e_i/T \ll 1$ to $e_i/T \gg 1$ and one finds that not only does $F(p(e_i)) = a + be_i$ for all e_i/T , but that $(1 + ke_i/T)^{1/k}$ maximizes entropy for all e_i/T .

Here we argue that one may have a distribution such that $F(p(e_i)) = a + be_i$, satisfying the moment average idea discussed above. Furthermore, $p(e_i) = g(p(e_i))^{1/k}$ such that for $e_i/T \ll 1$, one has the MB case, and for $e_i/T \gg 1$, one has the power law case. This means that in the two asymptotic limits one has maximization of entropy, but if a special function is required to join one limit to the other, then for e_i/T not in the asymptotic region, one does not have conservation of entropy. We suggest that this is the Kaniadakis case with the special function being $\sqrt[1+k]{1+kx}$ with $x = -e_i/T$.

The Notion of Moments

In (1), we suggest that if one uses a MaxEnt approach with constraints which are averages of moments of e_i/T , then the statistical approximation of the physical system is based on these averages. If one wishes to maximize some function $G(p(e_i))$ and $p(e_i) > 0$ for all e_i , then $G(p(e_i))$ may be written as:

$$G(p(e_i)) = p(e_i) F(p(e_i)) \quad ((1))$$

((1)) is also in the form of an average, and one may expand $p(e_i)$ and hence $F(p(e_i))$ in terms of powers of e_i/T . We thus argue that

$$F(p(e_i)) = a + be_i \quad ((2)) \quad \text{For constraints } \sum_i p(e_i) = 1 \text{ and } \sum_i e_i p(e_i) = e_{ave}$$

In order that the average ((1)) contain no more statistical information than the constraints. We note that the condition ((2)) holds for the Maxwell-Boltzmann, Tsallis and Kaniadakis cases. In ((1)), we also show how the form ((1)) leads to solutions which maximize entropy subject to the constraints of averages of moments.

MaxEnt

We consider the idea of maximization of entropy subject to the constraint given in ((2)). In such a case:

$$F(p) + p \frac{dF}{dp} \text{ matching } c + de_i \quad ((3))$$

If ((2)) holds then: $p \frac{dF}{dp} = a + b e_i$ as well.

A simple case is $p \frac{dF}{dp} = \text{constant}$ which holds for $F = \ln(p)$ and $F = p^k$. ((4))

This ultimately leads to the MB and Tsallis cases as discussed in (1).

Thus, we think in terms of $\ln(p)$ and a p^k and next focus on $e_i/T \ll 1$ and $e_i/T \gg 1$ limits.

$e_i/T \ll 1$ and $e_i/T \gg 1$ Limits

If $F(p) = p(e_i)^k$, then to satisfy ((2)) $p(e_i) = (a + be_i)^{1/k}$. ((4))

Such a form may also satisfy maximization of entropy locally, i.e. for all e_i regions.

The linear form in ((4)) becomes for $e_i/T \ll 1$ $a + be_i/k$ which is linked to

$$a \ln(1 + be_i/ka) \quad ((5))$$

The $e_i/T \ll 1$ limit is associated with $\ln(p)$. Given that $-p \ln(p)$ maximizes entropy for all e_i/T values, it must do so in the $e_i/T \ll 1$ range.

For the $e_i/T \gg 1$ range, one has automatically $(a + be_i/T)^{1/k}$ which becomes $(be_i/T)^{1/k}$. This power law also maximizes entropy in the $e_i/T \gg 1$ range.

The question one may ask is the following: What if one has:

$$(1 + e_i/T + .5 e_i^2/TT) \text{ for } p(e_i) \text{ in the } e_i/T \ll 1 \text{ limit?} \quad ((6))$$

In this case, the $e_i/T \ll 1$ limit mimics the MB distribution to second order in e_i/T , but for the $e_i/T \gg 1$ limit, one wishes to have

$$(e_i/T)^{1/k} \quad ((7))$$

This means that one no longer uses $(a+be^{i/T})$ power $1/k$ for the distribution as in the Tsallis case. A fundamental issue which then arises is:

One must have a special function which allows the quadratic $e^{i/T}$ term in ((6)) (i.e. the $e^{i/T} \ll 1$ limit) to become a linear term $(e^{i/T})$ power $1/k$ in the $e^{i/T}$ limit. This special function represents extra information we argue and so in the region between the two asymptotic limits one does not have maximum entropy because of this extra information. In particular, the function is:

$$\sqrt{1+kx} \text{ where } x=-e^{i/T}. \text{ In the } x \gg 1 \text{ limit one has: } kx \quad ((8))$$

$$\text{This leads to an } F(p) = \frac{1}{2k} (p^k - p^{-k}) \quad ((9))$$

Then an entropy formed via $\int p F(p)$ is only maximum in the $e^{i/T} \ll 1$ and $e^{i/T} \gg 1$ regions, but not in general. We suggest that is what happens for the Kaniadaksi case for which $F(p)$ is given by ((9)) and

$$p(e^{i/T}) = \{ \sqrt{1+kx} + kx \} \text{ power } 1/k \text{ with } x = -e^{i/T} \quad ((10))$$

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argued in (1) that in the case of maximizing a function $G(p)$, this function may be written as $\int p(e^{i/T}) G(p(e^{i/T}))$ as long as $p(e^{i/T}) > 0$. This product is of the form of an average of $G(p(e^{i/T}))$, but this function may be expanded in terms of moments of $e^{i/T}$ (i.e. powers of $e^{i/T}$). The constraints on the other hand, are a finite set of averages of moments, usually of the zeroth and first. In (1), we suggested that if the constraints represent a statistical approximation of the physical system based on the two average moments, then $F(p(e^{i/T}))$ should also only represent these two moments, i.e. $F(p(e^{i/T})) = a + be^{i/T}$. From this we showed that one may have $F(p) = \ln(p)$ or $F(p) = c + d p(e^{i/T})$ power k , i.e. obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann and Tsallis distributions.

Here we consider the $e^{i/T} \ll 1$ limit of $p(e^{i/T})$ and show that it should approach the MB limit. For $e^{i/T} \gg 1$, one could have the power law limit arise. In the Tsallis case, the form $p(e^{i/T}) = (1 - ke^{i/T})$ power $1/k$ satisfies both limits and so no extra information is required for $e^{i/T}$ values in between the two limits. We show, however, that if one wishes to match the MB distribution in the $e^{i/T} \ll 1$ limit to second order, $(1 + kx + .5k^2x^2)$ power $1/k$ where $x = -e^{i/T}$, then one requires a special function, namely $\sqrt{1+kx}$ to allow for the $(\)$ form to become x power $1/k$ in the $e^{i/T} \gg 1$ limit. This extra information means that for $e^{i/T}$ values not in the $e^{i/T} \ll 1$ or $e^{i/T} \gg 1$ ranges. We suggest that this is the reason that the Kaniadaksi entropy $\int p F(p)$ with $F(p) = \frac{1}{2k} (p^k - p^{-k})$ only represents maximum entropy in the $e^{i/T} \ll 1$ and $e^{i/T} \gg 1$ regions, but not in general as in the Tsallis case. $p(x) = \{ \sqrt{1+kx} + kx \} \text{ power } 1/k$ for the Kaniadakis case.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. MB and Tsallis Distributions, MaxEnt and the Notion of Moments of $e^{i/T}$ (preprint, zenodo, 2026)